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Determinants of Employee Behavior in the Pharmaceutical Industry: A Thematic Literature Review

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Abstract: *This is a review paper on factors that influence employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry. Objectives of study include thematically analyze and differentiate the literature, identify factors influencing, classify the identified factors into thematic categories, explain the observed relationships between the thematic categories, the identified factors, and employee behavior. During this study, we have reviewed 90 literatures published between 1976 to 2025. Afterward each paper is thematically categorized and analyzed for the most frequent category of factor influencing employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry. This paper found that employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry is affected by leadership and management practices and policies, Nature of work and work environment, psychological and physical state of employees at workplace and work time, and social environment which affect employees in day to day workplace.*

Keywords: *Pharmaceutical industry; Employee behavior; Organizational behavior; Work environment; Organizational culture; Human resource practices*

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the pharmaceutical industry has been growing substantially. Many major economies like India and China have a large part of their GDP coming from the pharmaceutical industry. The pharmaceutical industry has been a major part of imports for American, African, and European countries from major pharmaceutical producer countries like India and China. So, over the past few decades, many pharmaceutical companies have grown from small firms to global giants. The pharmaceutical industry has become more competitive for new entrants, strategically important for countries, and a source of employment for economies. This rise of pharmaceutical companies has triggered the development of new drugs and research activities in the medical field. These research and development activities, various mass production activities, rigorous quality checks, and regulatory compliance require very highly skilled employees to oversee them.

The working of the pharmaceutical industry directly affects the health of society. So, to remain a market leader in a highly competitive market, engaging pioneering in research ahead of others, ensuring regulatory compliance from various authorities, and adopting new emerging technologies require a very skilled workforce. This workforce has to follow very strict regulatory rules and maintain highly ethical behavior. Despite that, employers expect high productivity from them, leading to overworking and harsh conditions in organizations. Therefore, studying which factors affect employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry is very important.

1.1. Problem Statement

To remain competitive and relevant in the industry, pharmaceutical companies need to attract a highly skilled workforce. Due to the competitive environment, high workload and overtime are common occurrences in the pharmaceutical industry. Pharmaceutical companies also have high expectations of their workforce. Employees have to face high work expectations from employers along with various challenges such as maintaining ethical conduct during work hours, balancing work and life, coping with work stress, ensuring safety in the workplace, and meeting regulatory compliance requirements from multiple authorities and stakeholders.

To remain productive in this challenging work environment, employees must remain motivated and satisfied, which can be expressed as employee behavior. This employee behavior is mainly affected by various factors related to employees' personal factors and factors associated with the environmental conditions around them.

1.2. Objectives of the Study

- a) To thematically analyze and differentiate the literature into different categories.
- b) To identify factors influencing employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry.
- c) To classify the identified factors into thematic categories based on their similarities.
- d) To explain the observed relationships between the thematic categories, the identified factors, and employee behavior.

1.3. Significance of the Study

This study will identify various factors affecting employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry. Pharmaceutical companies can use the findings from this paper to formulate workforce related policies and strategies. Human resource departments and training institutes can use these findings to develop training plans for employees in the pharmaceutical industry. Academicians can use this paper for further studies on the topic of employee behavior in various other industries.

The findings from this paper will help pharmaceutical companies increase employee motivation and job satisfaction. This will lead to increased productivity, enhanced research and development, and increased employee retention of a skilled workforce.

1.4. Theoretical Frameworks

For this review, we studied Social Exchange Theory and the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) model. This model provided a solid Theoretical ground for the development of a conceptual idea on employee behavior in industry practices.

1.4.1. Social Exchange Theory:

The employee would expect organization to maintain fairness in appraisal and promotional strategies and obligation to protect his economic interest and physical safety using compensation, and safety practices, While company expects employees to be productive and motivated to work.

Social exchange theory mainly focuses on the relationship between the employee and the organization. This relationship is driven by mutual agreement on certain terms by both parties. The organization is expected to maintain fairness toward employees and have certain obligations toward them, while employees respond in return with commitment and trust toward the organization. A breach of this agreement leads to politics within organizational premises and gaps between actual organizational values and practices.

Employees expect the organization to maintain fairness in appraisal and promotional practices and to fulfill obligations to protect their economic interests and physical safety through compensation and safety practices. In return, the company expects employees to be productive and motivated to work.

1.4.2. Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model:

The Job Demands–Resources model consists of two parts: job demands and job resources. Job demands are associated with stress generated from workload, while job resources are associated with factors that reduce job demands, help employees achieve goals, and promote growth. Both job demands and job resources affect employee well-being and work performance. A well-proportioned balance between job demands and job resources is very important for maintaining motivated employee behavior.

1.4.3. Application of Frameworks in the Pharmaceutical Industry:

The pharmaceutical industry is competitive in nature, involves a lot of research and development, and has high work pressure. The workforce involved in the pharmaceutical industry is always under high expectations and work stress.

As per social exchange theory, to motivate employees, organizations must maintain fairness toward employees and fulfill obligations to provide sufficient safety and compensation. As per the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) model, employers must provide sufficient job resources to employees so that job stress is minimized.

As both models indicate, in the pharmaceutical industry, leadership, employee citizenship, fair compensation, organizational culture, working conditions, and safety factors play a significant role in shaping employee behavior toward the organization.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study will conduct a qualitative literature review to examine factors influencing employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry. Rather than following a full systematic review protocol, this study follows a structured and transparent narrative review process, commonly used in theory-building and conceptual integration studies.

2.1 Research Design:

The review was conducted in three sequential stages:

1. Structured identification and screening of relevant literature
2. Thematic analysis of selected literature
3. Organize and explain observed relationships.

This design enables the study to move beyond simple aggregation of findings and toward conceptual integration across multiple levels of analysis.

Fig. 1 PRISMA Diagram

2.2 Data Sources and Search Strategy:

Relevant studies were identified from four major academic databases: Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and JSTOR. Searches were conducted using combinations of keywords such as:

pharmaceutical industry, employee behavior, organizational culture, organizational behavior, motivation, job satisfaction, work engagement, job stress

Only peer-reviewed journal articles and selected high-quality review papers were considered. Reference lists of key articles were also examined to identify additional relevant studies.

2.3 *Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:*

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies focused on employee behaviour within the pharmaceutical industry or closely related pharmaceutical work contexts
- Studies examining factors influence employee behavior
- Studies published from 1976 and 2025
- Studies published in the English language

Exclusion criteria:

- Studies focused exclusively on clinical, chemical, or manufacturing process optimization without addressing employee behaviour
- Studies unrelated to workplace dynamics or organizational behaviour
- Opinion pieces, commentaries, and conceptual essays without empirical grounding

Based on these criteria, approximately 90 peer-reviewed articles were retained for final thematic analysis.

Publication Period	No. of Studies	Percentage (%)
Before 2000	17	18.89
2000 – 2004	5	5.56
2005 – 2009	10	11.11
2010 – 2014	11	12.22
2015 – 2019	19	21.11
2020 – 2025	28	31.11
Total	90	100

Table 1: Year-wise Distribution of Included Studies (N = 90)

2.4 *Process of Analysis:*

This review uses thematic analysis as the primary research tool. Each identified study is screened for various factors affecting employee behavior based on its findings and conclusions. These factors are then categorized into main themes, as mentioned in Table 3.

2.5 *Ethical Considerations:*

As this study is based exclusively on secondary data from published sources, no direct human participation was involved. All original sources were appropriately acknowledged and cited to ensure academic integrity and to avoid plagiarism.

3. THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE

The selected studies were analyzed using thematic analysis. Key variables, findings, and theoretical interpretations were extracted from each article and coded into preliminary category.

The information in the table no. 2 illustrates the thematic categorization of the Studies Included in the Review:

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
1	Ng et al. (2024)	Ethical Climate, Leadership, Corporate Social Responsibility	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Leadership & Management
2	Bowen (2004)	Ethical Climate, Organizational Culture, Communication, Innovation, Counseling	Organizational Culture, Communication Practices, Learning, Innovation & Change, Organizational Support
3	Singh and Jayanti (2013)	Institutional Logics, Role Interpretations, Social Knowledge	Organizational Culture, Work Design & Job Characteristics
4	Bhatia et al. (2025)	Power Struggle, Relationship Conflict, Resource Constraints, Role Conflict, Workforce Diversity	Leadership & Management, Social & Relational Context, Work Design & Job Characteristics, Organizational Support
5	Bhatia et al. (2024)	Emotional Intelligence, Power Struggle, Relationship Conflict, Resource Constraints, Role Conflict, Workforce Diversity	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Leadership & Management, Social & Relational Context, Work Design & Job Characteristics
6	Moideenkutty et al. (2001)	Organizational Support, Fairness, Communication, Leadership, Interpersonal Relationship	Organizational Support, Organizational Justice, Communication Practices, Leadership & Management, Social & Relational Context
7	Finne et al. (2016)	Organizational Support, Leadership, HR Practices, Role Conflict, Organizational Culture	Organizational Support, Leadership & Management, HR Practices, Work Design & Job Characteristics, Organizational Culture
8	Rahim et al. (2024)	Risk Culture, Employee Satisfaction Employee Engagement	Organizational Culture, Employee Well-Being & Health, Employee Engagement
9	Khan et al. (2025)	Job Autonomy, Occupational Self-Efficacy, Leadership, Career Growth	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Motivation & Psychological Resources, Leadership & Management, HR Practices
10	Zhong et al. (2015)	HR Practices, Organizational Support, Organizational Culture	HR Practices, Organizational Support, Organizational Culture
11	Sundgren et al. (2005)	Job Autonomy, Training and Development, Communication	Work Design & Job Characteristics, HR Practices, Communication Practices
12	Bamberger and Phillips (1991)	Organizational Culture, Compensation, Staffing and Appraisal, Training and Development	Organizational Culture, Employment Conditions, HR Practices

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
13	Ruble et al. (2021)	Emotional Intelligence	Motivation & Psychological Resources
14	MacLean et al. (2014)	Ethical Climate, Trust	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Social & Relational Context
15	Chaudhry et al. (2016)	Leadership, HR Practices	Leadership & Management, HR Practices
16	Nambudiri (2012)	Management Policies , Work Environment	Leadership & Management, Work Environment Quality
17	Munir et al. (2015)	Interpersonal Trust And Transformational Leadership Styles	Social & Relational Context, Leadership & Management
18	Fernandes et al. (2023)	Organizational Culture	Organizational Culture
19	Maltarich et al. (2017)	Compensation	Employment Conditions
20	Hameed et al. (2021)	Job Autonomy, Opportunities For Advancement, Involved Communication, And Decisive Action	Work Design & Job Characteristics, HR Practices, Leadership & Management
21	Wang et al. (2025)	Ethical Climate, Leadership, Financial Job Dependency	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Leadership & Management, Employment Conditions
22	Mateen et al. (2022)	HR Practices, Corporate Social Responsibility	HR Practices, Ethics, CSR & Governance
23	Phipps et al. (2012)	Leadership, Interpersonal Relationship, Compensation	Leadership & Management, Social & Relational Context, Employment Conditions
24	D'Amato and Zijlstra (2008)	Management Policies , Work Environment, HR Practices, Self-Efficacy	Leadership & Management, Work Environment Quality, HR Practices, Motivation & Psychological Resources
25	Diamantidis and Chatzoglou (2018)	Intrinsic Motivation, Adaptability, Management Support, Job Environment, And Organizational Climate, Job Environment, Job Autonomy, Job Communication,	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Leadership & Management, Work Design & Job Characteristics, Communication Practices
26	Michie and West (2004)	Organizational Culture, HRM Practices, Job Design, Leadership, Employee Health, Stress, Satisfaction, Motivation	Organizational Culture, HR Practices, Work Design & Job Characteristics, Employee Well-Being & Health, Leadership & Management
27	Pfeffer (2007)	job dissatisfaction, distrust, disengagement, management practices, job attitudes	Employee Well-Being & Health, Social & Relational Context, Leadership & Management

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
28	S. K. Singh and Singh (2018)	Organizational Justice, Psychological Empowerment	Organizational Justice, Motivation & Psychological Resources
29	O'Hara et al. (1985)	Organizational Behavior Management (OBM) Methods, Reinforcement Strategies, Performance Feedback, Behavioral Interventions	HR Practices, Leadership & Management
30	Wright and Cropanzano (2000)	Job Stress, Psychological Well-Being, Physical Health, Organizational Behavior Practices	Employee Well-Being & Health, Work Environment Quality
31	Manuti and Giancaspro (2019)	Autonomy, Leadership, Communication, Organizational Mindfulness, Commitment to Resilience, Work Engagement, Psychological Capital	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Leadership & Management, Communication Practices, Motivation & Psychological Resources, Employee Engagement
32	García-Morales et al. (2011)	Internal Communication, Technological Proactivity, Organizational Learning	Communication Practices, Learning, Innovation & Change
33	Chang et al. (2021)	Corporate Social Responsibility, Organizational Identification	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Social & Relational Context
34	Crispin et al. (2023)	Psychosocial Safety Climate, Workplace Conditions, Work-Related Stress	Work Environment Quality, Employee Well-Being & Health
35	Trincherro et al. (2017)	Supervisor–Employee Relationships, Psychological Capital	Social & Relational Context, Motivation & Psychological Resources
36	Martin et al. (2005)	Psychological Climate (perceptions of organization and work environment)	Organizational Culture
37	David-Barrett et al. (2017)	Culture Clash, Commercial Tension, Reliance on Local Agents, Board-Level Commitment to Anti-Bribery Programs, Incentive and Remuneration Practices	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Organizational Culture
38	Lee (2019)	Organizational Culture, Organizational Capabilities for Care Services	Organizational Culture, Organizational Support
39	Lucas et al. (2017)	Workplace Dignity, Safe and Secure Working Conditions	Work Environment Quality, Employee Well-Being & Health
40	Sverke (2009)	Workplace Relationships, Organizational Support, Job Characteristics	Social & Relational Context, Organizational Support, Work Design & Job Characteristics
41	Tasoulis et al. (2023)	Perceived Organizational Support, Empowerment, Tenure, Planned Organizational Culture Change	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Organizational Culture, Learning, Innovation & Change

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
		Initiatives	
42	Donald et al. (2005)	Psychological Well-Being, Organizational Commitment, Access to Resources, Work Environment Factors	Employee Well-Being & Health, Organizational Support, Work Environment Quality
43	Li et al. (2023)	Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) Practices, Psychological Green Climate	HR Practices, Organizational Culture
44	Kronus (1976)	Work Setting Power Structure, Organizational Context, Role Orientation	Leadership & Management, Organizational Culture
45	Chien and Lin (2012)	Developmental HR Configurations, Psychological Contracts	HR Practices, Social & Relational Context
46	Wang et al. (2021b)	Coordination, Psychological Safety, Job Security	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Employee Well-Being & Health, Employment Conditions
47	Tsai (2011)	organizational culture, leadership	Organizational Culture, Leadership & Management
48	Hoxha et al. (2024b)	Organizational Culture, Supportive Work Environment, Optimized Work Processes	Work Environment Quality, Learning, Innovation & Change
49	Terborg (1981)	Traits, Cognitions, Values, Organizational Context, Job Conditions	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Work Design & Job Characteristics
50	Ye et al. (2022)	Organizational Health-Oriented Strategies, Psychological Wellbeing, Employee Trust	Employee Well-Being & Health, Social & Relational Context, Leadership & Management
51	Akerboom and Maes (2006)	Job Demands, Decision Authority, Organizational Risk Factors, Communication, Staffing Resources, Organizational Support	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Leadership & Management, Work Environment Quality
52	Aggarwal et al. (2022)	Error Management Culture, Perceived Procedural Justice, Customer–Employee Exchange, Employee Engagement	Learning, Innovation & Change, Organizational Justice, Social & Relational Context, Employee Engagement
53	Arslan and Roudaki (2018)	Organizational Cynicism, Psychological Contract Breach	Social & Relational Context, Organizational Support
54	Latta (2020)	Organizational Culture Dynamics, Leadership Style, Employee Engagement	Organizational Culture, Leadership & Management, Employee Engagement
55	Cha et al.	Person–Organization Fit on Prosocial	Social & Relational Context

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
	(2013)	Identity	
56	Islam & Tariq (2018)	Perceived Learning Organizational Environment, Employee Engagement	Learning, Innovation & Change, Employee Engagement
57	Sell and Cleal (2011)	Social Support, Information on Decisions, Influence, Rewards	Work Environment Quality, Employment Conditions
58	Kilcullen et al. (2022)	Leadership Commitment, Communication, Learning, Accountability	Organizational Culture
59	Morton et al. (2019)	Psychological Empowerment, Trust, Supportive Supervisor–Employee Relationships	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Social & Relational Context
60	Joslin et al. (2010)	Perceived Acceptance, Work Standards	Social & Relational Context, Work Design & Job Characteristics
61	Hyde, Harris and Boaden (2013)	Organizational Culture, Altruism, Conscientiousness, HR Values	Organizational Culture, Motivation & Psychological Resources
62	Rantz, Scott and Porter (1996)	Interpersonal Relations, Recognition, Nature of Work, Responsibility	Social & Relational Context, Employment Conditions, Work Design & Job Characteristics
63	Biddison et al. (2016)	Safety Culture	Organizational Culture
64	Jamal (1990)	Job Stress, Role Ambiguity, Role Overload, Role Conflict, Resource Inadequacy, Type-A Behavior	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Employee Well-Being & Health
65	Huhtala et al. (2015)	Ethical Climate	Ethics, CSR & Governance
66	Welsch and LaVan (1981)	Role Conflict, Role Ambiguity, Participative Climate, Power, Teamwork, Job Satisfaction, Promotion Opportunities	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Leadership & Management, Social & Relational Context
67	Efraty and Sirgy (1990)	Quality of Work Life, Need Satisfaction, Organizational Resources	Employee Well-Being & Health, Organizational Support
68	Fuselier and Tanja (1975)	Opportunity for Expression and Development, Wages and Hours, Leadership Fairness, Interest in Work, Recognition, Safe Work Conditions, Economic Security	Employment Conditions, Leadership & Management, Work Environment Quality
69	Stucki (1980)	Organizational Structure, Leadership Approach	Organizational Culture, Leadership & Management

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
70	Balthazard, Cooke and Potter (2006)	Organizational Culture Norms, Communication, Role Clarity, Organizational Fit	Organizational Culture, Communication Practices, Work Design & Job Characteristics
71	Helfrich et al. (2007)	Organizational Culture Types	Organizational Culture
72	Agho, Mueller and Price (1993)	Environmental Factors, Job Characteristics, Personality Traits	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Motivation & Psychological Resources
73	Cooke and Rousseau (1988)	Behavioral Norms, Shared Values, Organizational Culture	Organizational Culture
74	Chalupsky (1964)	Incentive Practices (Recognition, Promotions, Merit Pay, Challenging Work), Supervisory Appraisal	HR Practices, Employment Conditions
75	Sussmann and Vecchio (1982)	Social Influence, Individual Differences, Organizational Typology	Social & Relational Context, Motivation & Psychological Resources
76	Keller, Szilagyi and Holland (1977)	Job Characteristics, Interpersonal Relations	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Social & Relational Context
77	Zhang et al. (2025)	Subjective Norms, Face Concern, Reciprocal Benefit, Psychological Ownership of Knowledge, Execution Cost	Social & Relational Context, Motivation & Psychological Resources
78	Kahaleh and Gaither (2005)	Power Factors, Need for Achievement, Psychological Empowerment, Structural Empowerment	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Leadership & Management
79	Campbell, Arrowood and Kelm (2013)	Positive Work Culture, Employee Beliefs, Attitudes, Organizational Ideologies	Organizational Culture
80	Mahmood et al. (2025)	Work-Family Conflict, Psychological Flexibility, Workload	Work Design & Job Characteristics, Employee Well-Being & Health
81	Tollman et al. (2016)	Organizational Effectiveness, Individual Incentives, Goal Alignment, Cooperative Context	Leadership & Management, HR Practices
82	Sun, Mo and Nie (2022)	Organizational Learning, Role-Breadth Self-Efficacy, Resilience	Learning, Innovation & Change, Motivation & Psychological Resources
83	Falola, Ogueyungbo and Ojebola (2020)	Recognition, Employee Wellbeing, Learning and Development, Diversity and Inclusion	HR Practices, Employee Well-Being & Health

Sr. No.	Author	Affecting Factors	Thematic Categories
84	Duggan, Cormican and McDermott (2022)	Personality Traits, Affective Organizational Commitment, Leadership Support	Motivation & Psychological Resources, Leadership & Management
85	Glaveli et al. (2025)	Corporate Social Responsibility, Employee Trust	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Social & Relational Context
86	Shepard, Clifton and Kruse (1996)	Flexible Work Hours, Job Attitudes, Work-Related Stress, Absenteeism	Employment Conditions, Employee Well-Being & Health
87	Geary and Dobbins (2001)	Prior Teamwork Experience, Management Strategy, HRM Practices, Union Presence	Leadership & Management, HR Practices, Organizational Culture
88	Church, Margiloff and Coruzzi (1995)	Work-Group Climate, Managerial Behavior, Goal and Role Clarity	Organizational Culture, Leadership & Management
89	Lin et al. (2018)	Ethical Climate, Likelihood of Detection, Performance Pressure	Ethics, CSR & Governance, Leadership & Management
90	Falola et al. (2020)	Recognition, Employee Wellbeing, Learning and Development, Diversity and Inclusion	HR Practices, Employee Well-Being & Health

Table 2: Thematic Categorization of the Studies Included in The Review

Thematic Categories	Factors Affecting Employee Behavior
Leadership & Management	Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Leadership Style, Leadership Commitment, Leadership Fairness, Leadership Support, Management Policies, Management Support, Management Strategy, Supervisory Appraisal, Managerial Behavior, Decision Authority
Organizational Culture	Organizational Culture, Risk Culture, Safety Culture, Culture Clash, Organizational Climate, Psychological Climate, Organizational Culture Dynamics, Organizational Culture Norms, Organizational Culture Types, Shared Values, Behavioral Norms, Organizational Ideologies
Work Design & Job Characteristics	Job Autonomy, Job Characteristics, Role Conflict, Role Ambiguity, Role Overload, Role Clarity, Workload, Job Conditions, Nature of Work, Responsibility, Work Standards, Flexible Work Hours, Job Security
Social & Relational Context	Interpersonal Relationships, Workplace Relationships, Supervisor–Employee Relationships, Interpersonal Trust, Teamwork, Social Support, Social Influence, Workforce Diversity, Coordination, Cooperative Context, Customer–Employee Exchange, Person–Organization Fit
HR Practices	HR Practices, Staffing and Appraisal, Training and Development,

Thematic Categories	Factors Affecting Employee Behavior
	Career Growth, Promotions, Merit Pay, Performance Feedback, Incentive Practices, Developmental HR Configurations, HRM Practices, Green HRM Practices, Union Presence
Motivation & Psychological Resources	Intrinsic Motivation, Psychological Capital, Self-Efficacy, Psychological Empowerment, Need for Achievement, Adaptability, Resilience, Psychological Flexibility, Personality Traits, Cognitions, Values, Psychological Ownership
Employee Well-Being & Health	Employee Satisfaction, Psychological Well-Being, Physical Health, Job Stress, Work-Related Stress, Burnout, Quality of Work Life, Work-Family Conflict, Absenteeism, Employee Wellbeing, Health-Oriented Strategies
Ethics, CSR & Governance	Ethical Climate, Corporate Social Responsibility, Governance Practices, Anti-Bribery Programs, Likelihood of Detection, Financial Job Dependency, Performance Pressure
Work Environment Quality	Work Environment, Workplace Conditions, Safe and Secure Working Conditions, Psychosocial Safety Climate, Environmental Factors, Ergonomic Conditions
Employment Conditions	Compensation, Wages and Hours, Economic Security, Employment Contracts, Promotion Opportunities, Rewards, Individual Incentives
Communication Practices	Communication, Internal Communication, Job Communication, Information on Decisions, Involved Communication, Communication Climate
Organizational Support	Organizational Support, Perceived Organizational Support, Access to Resources, Staffing Resources, Supportive Work Environment
Learning, Innovation & Change	Organizational Learning, Innovation, Learning and Development, Technological Proactivity, Error Management Culture, Planned Organizational Culture Change Initiatives
Employee Engagement	Employee Engagement, Work Engagement, Organizational Commitment, Engagement Climate, Goal Alignment
Organizational Justice	Organizational Justice, Procedural Justice, Distributive Justice, Interactional Justice, Fairness, Psychological Contract Breach, Organizational Cynicism

Table3: Thematic Categories and Respective Factors Affecting Employee Behavior

The following table illustrates the frequency distribution of Thematic Categories used during the categorization of factors affecting employee behavior.

Sr. No.	Thematic Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Leadership & Management	42	47%
2	Organizational Culture	31	34%
3	Work Design & Job Characteristics	30	33%
4	Social & Relational Context	28	31%

5	HR Practices	22	24%
6	Motivation & Psychological Resources	21	23%
7	Employee Well-Being & Health	20	22%
8	Ethics, CSR & Governance	13	14%
9	Work Environment Quality	13	14%
10	Employment Conditions	13	14%
11	Communication Practices	11	12%
12	Organizational Support	11	12%
13	Learning, Innovation & Change	10	11%
14	Employee Engagement	6	7%
15	Organizational Justice	4	4%

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of 'Categories of Factors Affecting Employee Behavior'

4. DISCUSSION

Leadership and management emerge as the most prominent categories of factors influencing employee behavior. These factors strongly reflect the principles of Social Exchange Theory, as effective leadership upholds organizational commitment toward employees by ensuring fairness, support, and recognition, while simultaneously reducing job demands and work-related stressors through adequate managerial support and resource allocation. Strong leadership has consistently been a critical determinant of organizational effectiveness. In the pharmaceutical industry, functional areas such as research and development, manufacturing operations, quality assurance, regulatory affairs, marketing, and sales are strategically vital and require a highly skilled workforce. Employees operating within these units are frequently exposed to high workloads, performance pressure, and strict regulatory requirements. In such demanding conditions, the presence of transformational and supportive leadership plays a crucial role in enhancing employee commitment, motivation, and trust toward the organization, ultimately leading to improved productivity and sustainable organizational performance.

Organizational Culture, Work Design & Job Characteristics, and Social & Relational Context are the second most frequent categories of factors affecting employee behavior. All three categories Organizational Culture, Work Design & Job Characteristics, and Social & Relational Context can be correlated with the nature of work and the work environment. All three categories are related to job demand of JD-R model and social exchange theory's relationship between employer and employee. In the pharmaceutical industry, rather than individual effort, team efforts matter more. Tasks involved in the pharmaceutical industry are largely intellectual and problem-solving in nature. Individual efforts sometimes are not able to solve critical problems, but group efforts can help solve these problems through collaboration. Therefore, a positive and conducive nature of work and work environment is very helpful in promoting positive employee behavior and reducing work-related stress.

HR Practices, Motivation & Psychological Resources, and Employee Well-Being & Health are categories that moderately influence employee behavior in the pharmaceutical industry. These categories are closely associated with the psychological and physical state of employees while performing their work. Effective HR practices such as training and development, career growth opportunities, fair appraisal systems, and recognition help enhance employees' motivation, self-efficacy, and psychological empowerment. At the same time, employee well-being and health-related factors such as job stress, work-family balance, and

quality of work life directly affect employees' ability to sustain productive and ethical behavior in a high-pressure pharmaceutical work environment. From the perspective of the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) model, these categories function as key job resources that help employees cope with high job demands inherent in pharmaceutical research, production, quality control, and regulatory compliance activities. In line with Social Exchange Theory, supportive HR practices and well-being initiatives strengthen employees' trust, commitment, and reciprocal positive behavior toward the organization.

Ethics, CSR & Governance, Work Environment Quality, Employment Conditions, Communication Practices, Organizational Support, and Learning, Innovation & Change collectively represent factors associated with the social environment of the pharmaceutical workplace. These categories reflect the broader organizational and social context within which employees interact with management, colleagues, and institutional systems on a day-to-day basis. In the pharmaceutical industry, where ethical compliance, regulatory accountability, and transparency are critical, ethical climate, governance practices, and CSR initiatives strongly influence employees' perceptions of organizational integrity and fairness. Similarly, work environment quality, employment conditions, and organizational support shape employees' sense of security, dignity, and belonging within the organization. Communication practices and learning-oriented environments facilitate information sharing, coordination, and continuous skill development, which are essential in research-driven and compliance-intensive pharmaceutical operations. From the perspective of Social Exchange Theory, these social environmental factors reinforce reciprocal relationships between employees and organizations by fostering trust, support, and shared responsibility.

5. FINDINGS, RESEARCH GAPS, AND LIMITATION

5.1 Findings

This study identifies leadership and management practices play a dominant role in shaping employee commitment and performance. In addition, the nature of work and work environment, along with employees' psychological and physical state during work, significantly affect their behavior. The social environment of the workplace, including organizational culture, relationships, and support systems, also strongly influences employees' day-to-day behavior.

5.2 Research Gaps

The review indicates limited industry-specific and integrative research on employee behavior in the pharmaceutical sector. Most studies examine individual factors in isolation, with fewer studies adopting combined theoretical frameworks or longitudinal approaches.

5.3 Limitation

This study is based on secondary literature and does not follow a full systematic review or meta-analysis. The findings are also limited to English-language publications and are subject to interpretive bias in thematic categorization.

6. CONCLUSION

The findings highlight that employee behavior is primarily shaped by leadership and management practices, the nature of work and work environment, employees' psychological and physical well-being, and the broader social environment of the workplace.

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